

Total Care of the Elderly- A Multidisciplinary Approach

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The Changing Role of Geriatric Day Hospital

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The geriatric day hospital (GDH) was established with the aim of providing multi-disciplinary care for those elderly people in the community who would benefit from it. The development of GDH originated in psychiatric day hospitals, and was an attempt to break out from chronic institutions. Since the first purpose-built GDH was opened in Oxford in 1958, GDHs proliferated rapidly to 550 units in 1990s in the United Kingdom. In Hong Kong, GDHs have expanded from 1 in 1975 to 10 in 1995. GDH provides important links with other hospital services, residential care, and carers in the community; and has thus been described as the hub of the geriatric service.

The roles of a GDH can be acute or chronic; the former includes assessment, rehabilitation, medical/nursing procedures; while the latter includes maintenance and social care. Surveys in U.K. in 1970, 1980, and 1992 revealed a shift in emphasis of the role of GDH towards acute functions; focusing on short-stay attenders (assessment, rehabilitation, procedures) as opposed to longer stay attenders (maintenance, social care, respite). A similar trend of emphasis on the acute role of GDH is also seen in Hong Kong, as reflected by an increase in the overall corrected new patient index ($\text{new} \times 10 / \text{total}$) from 0.25 in 1979 to 0.64 in 1995. Several factors account for this change locally: (1) increased liaison with social services/day care centres to absorb social/maintenance cases; (2) geriatric wards becoming more acute; (3) regular review by geriatricians helps to prevent accumulation of chronic attenders; (4) utilization of the multi-disciplinary setting of GDHs to run some specialist clinics on continence, arthritis (as part of ortho-geriatric service) and rheumatology; (5) new referrals for once-only assessment, including for placement in residential homes; (6) adoption of performance indicator other than "total attendance" and emphasizing on efficiency; (7) switch of transport from ambulance to rehabilitation bus so that GDHs are less accessible to more disabled frail elderly people. There is debate whether the acute and chronic roles of GDH are compatible with each other and whether these roles should be separated into different types of GDHs with different therapist/nurse ratios (higher for the acute type, and lower for the chronic type). A progressive care model of GDH-day centre continuum could evolve to allow a smooth transition from rehabilitation to maintenance, so that a number can 'graduate' from GDH to day centre. Local outcome studies of GDHs have shown favourable results. The result of a current meta-analysis of worldwide GDH trials is awaited. However, the usefulness of such studies are limited by (1) the heterogeneity of day hospital attenders; (2) the changing

role of GDH; (3) no allowance for difference in outcome measurements for the acute and chronic roles of GDH.

In the recent year, GDH has also been used as a base for out-reach work for the community geriatric assessment service. A similar hybrid model of home rehabilitation-GDH has also been advocated by Young based on his Bradford study. The idea is to combine the benefits of home rehabilitation with the multi-disciplinary approach, which has been the main strength of the GDH. In line with a need-related approach, the lower age limit of some GDHs have also been relaxed to include younger stroke or hip fracture patients. Future development of GDH services should however consider not only cost, but also their effectiveness in relation to alternatives such as community rehabilitation. New models of GDH could evolve: resource centre, mobile team, mobile GDH, GDH-day centre. The appropriate model and role of GDH should be considered in the context of the health needs of the catchment population, and the local health and social services provision.

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